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Exploiting Enzyme Evolution for Computational Protein Design

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Abstract

Recent years have seen an explosion of interest in understanding the physico-chemical parameters that shape enzyme evolution, as well as substantial advances in computational enzyme design. This review will discuss three areas where evolutionary information can be used as part of the design process: (1) using ancestral sequence reconstruction (ASR) to generate new starting points for enzyme design efforts, (2) learning from how nature uses conformational dynamics in enzyme evolution to mimic this process *in silico* and (3) modular design of enzymes from smaller fragments, again mimicking the process by which nature appears to create new protein folds. Using showcase examples, we highlight the importance of incorporating evolutionary information to continue to push forward the boundaries of enzyme design studies.

Keywords

residue co-evolution | directed evolution | structural bioinformatics | conformational dynamics | enhanced sampling approaches

Computational Enzyme Design Based on Protein Evolution: An Overview

Roughly three decades have passed since the first attempts to design new enzymes using computational approaches [1, 2], and the field has matured considerably since then. While the earliest attempts at computational enzyme design focused primarily on side-chain positioning [1-4] or on focusing the search space for *in vitro* **directed evolution** (see Glossary) studies [5], subsequent work broadly expanded the scope of the field, including fully **de novo design** of new enzymes [6] (typically followed by optimization using directed evolution), and the repurposing of existing enzymes to catalyze ever more complex chemical reactions [7, 8]. In addition, computational design approaches are becoming ever more streamlined, such that there now exist a range of powerful web servers that can assist in the design process [9].

In principle, computational design approaches can take two very loosely defined directions: **structure-based approaches** that require some level of knowledge of the system of interest, including information about the chemical mechanisms, transition states and key catalytic residues involved, and **sequence-based approaches** that can, for example, draw on evolutionary information to predict potential hotspots for protein engineering as well as new variants with desired physicochemical properties, something that is in particular increasingly being achieved using **machine learning** approaches [10].

Computational approaches that require minimal knowledge of the molecular details of the chemical processes involved are attractive for their speed and efficiency, as exploring the underlying mechanisms and transition states typically requires significant experimental and/or

computational effort. However, much like their experimental counterparts, such approaches will likely hit “**optimization plateaus**” [11, 12], where further improvement in activity becomes extremely challenging, and without knowledge of the underlying chemistry, it can be difficult-to-impossible to overcome such plateaus. Therefore, rather than competing with each other, sequence- and structure-based approaches are highly complementary as each provides different types of insights into how to improve a given system. In addition, nature has already provided a blueprint for how new enzymes evolve, and by reconstructing **evolutionary trajectories** and probing the natural evolution of enzymes, we can learn from nature’s tricks to improve enzymes both *in vitro* and *in silico*.

Experimental “protein engineers turned evolutionists” [13] have had substantial progress in enzyme design using insights from natural evolution. However, there has also been significant progress in computational design studies based on evolutionary information, in particular due to increasing awareness of the role of conformational dynamics in the natural evolution of enzymes [12, 14-18], which is now being increasingly incorporated into the computational design process [15, 17]. In this review, we will discuss three directions where evolutionary information is being used to guide the computational design process, specifically: (1) repurposing of protein scaffolds identified through **ancestral sequence reconstruction (ASR)** as potential starting points for generating new enzyme activities, (2) harnessing conformational dynamics, a key driver of natural enzyme evolution, in computational enzyme design and (3) **modular design** processes based on identifying evolutionarily important sub-domain segments that can be rearranged to create new enzymes. These are just some of the current directions where evolutionary information can be used to drive the design process, but they showcase the potential of this field.

Repurposing Ancient Enzymes for New Catalytic Functions

While there are various ways evolutionary information can be used in enzyme design, one of the most obvious of these is the use of ancestral sequence reconstruction (ASR) to identify potential starting points for subsequent experimental or computational design effort. Enzymes obtained from ASR make attractive starting points for enzyme design, as they tend to be highly thermostable, conformationally flexible, and evolvable [19-21]. While many different computational algorithms exist with which to perform ASR (**Table 1**), the basic principle of all of these is to use the sequences of known, extant proteins, in order to reconstruct phylogenetic trees containing sequences of putative ancestors, based on the probability of finding a given amino acid substitution at the given point in amino acid sequence [22, 23]. Such ancestral inference yields a “cloud” of sequences that relate to putative historical ancestors [24-26], although typically only the most probabilistic of these sequences is subject to further experimental or computational characterization of the evolutionary trajectory.

There is of course doubt as to how realistic the sequence predictions from ASR actually are: as pointed out by Copley [27], due to ambiguities in the reconstruction, the probability of even the most probabilistic sequence being the real sequence is very low, as, in practice, many positions are predicted with a probability of <50%, in particular if the data set of extant proteins used for the reconstruction is highly diverged. In addition, particular challenges are posed by gaps in alignments (*i.e.* insertion/deletion evolutionary events), since different ways of dealing with these can lead to quite different sequences and phenotypes [28]. Furthermore, while many biochemical studies of reconstructed ancestral proteins suggest enhanced thermostability of the putative ancestors, it has been argued that there is a risk that this enhanced thermostability is a result of reconstruction bias rather than a true property of the putative ancestors (see detailed discussion in,

for instance, ref. [29]). However, a recent study has used experimental phylogenetics [30] to reproduce in the laboratory an evolutionary trajectory of a red fluorescent protein [24]. The advantage of this approach is that the sequences of the true ancestral nodes are actually known, and can be phenotypically characterized and compared to the sequences predicted by ASR. This study demonstrated that even though there exist some level of mistakes in the reconstructed sequences (which are exacerbated the more ancient the node), the phenotypes of the actual and reconstructed ancestors are similar. In addition, one can reconstruct multiple putative ancestors and compare their properties to increase the likelihood that one is observing the phenotypic properties of the “true” ancestor [27].

Clearly, however, while there are challenges in inferring actual evolutionary information through the use of ASR, what is obvious is that protein scaffolds obtained through ASR are excellent starting points for subsequent protein design effort due to their high thermostability and evolvability [31]. There have been a great number of experimental studies using ancestrally reconstructed proteins for enzyme design due to their greater thermostability; more recently, interest has also shifted to using ASR to obtain scaffolds that can be used as starting points for engineering of catalytic properties [22, 23, 27, 31]. Several such studies have focused specifically on using ASR to obtain flexible scaffolds that can be manipulated for engineering purposes in terms of their conformational properties. These will be discussed in more detail in the subsequent section. However, as some (out of many) other examples of recent success stories, ASR has been used to understand allosteric communication in a multienzyme complex of a key metabolic enzyme, tryptophan synthase [32, 33], to obtain a high redox potential laccase [34], to modulate the catalytic adaptability of an extremophile kinase [35], and to identify novel heme binding that

modulates allosteric regulation of an ancestral glycosidase (**Figure 1**) [36]. This latter study is notable, as heme binding was not observed in any of ~5500 crystal structures of ~1400 modern glycosidases. Experimental characterization of a number of modern glycosidases showed appreciable levels of heme binding, but significantly lower than that of the ancestral glycosidase, indicating that the ability to efficiently bind heme to allosterically regulate catalysis is a specific feature of the ancestral enzyme [36].

Overall, the use of evolutionary information obtained from ASR is a powerful tool for enzyme engineering, and with growing interest in using ASR to obtain enzymes with tailored catalytic properties [22, 31], it is likely that we will observe much greater usage of this technique in protein design in the coming years.

Harnessing Conformational Dynamics for Enzyme Engineering

Recent years have seen increasing awareness of the importance of conformational dynamics to **catalytic promiscuity** and **enzyme evolvability** [14, 15, 17, 18, 37]. This dates back to early work by James and Tawfik [14], who presented a model for the role of **conformational selection** in enzyme evolution, in which conformational plasticity allows enzymes to sample conformations that can bind new ligands and facilitate new chemistry. While such conformations may be only rarely sampled in the wild-type enzyme, evolutionary pressure can alter the ensemble such that a previously rare conformation becomes dominant, and a new activity becomes preferred. One would expect this phenomenon to be observed more frequently in laboratory than natural evolution, as in the laboratory, even low-level promiscuous activities can be detected and amplified, whereas natural evolution requires selective pressure to amplify a promiscuous activity. There are exceptions to this, however [38, 39], and the importance of conformational dynamics in

shaping enzyme evolutionary trajectories has been observed in both natural and artificial (directed) evolutionary trajectories [15-17]. Here, the fine-tuning of conformational dynamics to enhance activity has been proposed to occur in two ways: (1) increased sampling of states capable of conferring new catalytic activities and (2) reduced sampling of non-productive conformations [16]. Here, and in line with the rest of this review, our focus will be on computational studies, as learning from evolution and harnessing conformational dynamics in computational protein engineering is an actively growing area. We note that related methodological aspects have been recently reviewed in, for example, ref. [40], and a summary of selected methods is presented in **Table 1**. In addition, the field is growing continuously, and the number of user-friendly tools is growing accordingly [9].

A showcase model system for understanding the role of conformational dynamics in protein evolution and design, in particular from a computational perspective, have been β -lactamases, enzymes that are capable of hydrolyzing the lactam core of nearly all β -lactam antibiotics (including penicillin derivatives, cephalosporins and carbanapems), and are thus major contributors to bacterial antibiotic resistance [41]. In particular, the evolution of serine β -lactamases has been characterized extensively through ASR, and thoroughly characterized in terms of their biochemical and biophysical properties, including their structure, function and stability [42, 43]. Subsequent experimental and computational analysis suggested an important role for conformational dynamics in the evolvability of these enzymes, with a narrowing of the **conformational ensemble** upon transitioning from the Precambrian nodes to the more specialized modern enzymes [18, 20, 24, 43]. In addition, it has been suggested that mutations utilize **dynamic allostery** to confer antibiotic resistance in the modern TEM-1 β -lactamase [44], which is one of

the most commonly encountered β -lactamases in Gram-negative bacteria [45]. Interestingly, despite large differences in both sequence and scaffold flexibility, the overall tertiary structure remains largely unchanged over the course of these enzymes' evolution [46]. **Excess positional mutual information analysis** and MD simulations have been used to predict allosteric mutations that affect β -lactamase drug resistance [47] and **Markov State Models** have been used to identify hidden conformational states that are important for conferring antibiotic resistance [48], which can allow for the prediction of potential resistance to new compounds, and aid drug discovery efforts. Finally, the conformational flexibility at the Precambrian nodes could be exploited to insert a *de novo* active site capable of catalyzing Kemp eliminase activity [46], which could be further optimized [49] using ultra-low-throughput computational screening (using FuncLib [50]) to reach catalytic activities comparable to those of modern enzymes towards their natural substrates (**Figure 2**) [51].

Following from this, Kemp elimination is a model reaction for the base-catalyzed proton abstraction from carbon, and is one of the commonly targeted reactions in artificial enzyme design [52]. In related recent work [53], Chica and coworkers used molecular simulations in order to recapitulate the effect of the directed evolution of the most proficient Kemp eliminase designed to date, HG3.17 [54]. They then exploited changes in conformational dynamics during the evolutionary trajectory leading to HG3.17 from a *de novo* design, HG3 [55], in order to engineer a biocatalyst, HG4, with catalytic efficiencies close to that of HG3.17 but using only key first and second shell substitutions picked up during the evolutionary trajectory based on a template obtained using ensemble-based design.

Another group that has invested significant effort into understanding the role of conformational dynamics and **distal mutations** in enzyme catalysis and evolution are that of Osuna and coworkers. This includes, in 2017, the development of a new approach, the “Shortest Path Map” (SPM) [56]. This approach can be applied to molecular dynamics (MD) simulations to identify catalytically important communication pathways in proteins, as well as the pairs of residues with the highest contributions to the communication pathway. It has so far been successfully applied to either understand the evolution of catalysis and/or engineer the activity of retro-aldolases [56], tryptophan synthase [33, 57], monoamine oxidase [58], and, most recently, cytochrome P450 monooxygenase [59]. In this latter case, the authors were able to identify two mutations that initially affected only activity without a corresponding **shift in population** of conformations, and thus did not lead to a selectivity change. However, a third mutation identified using the SPM approach was able to modify the conformational ensemble and change both activity and selectivity. Further examples of approaches that can be used to predict distal mutations are discussed in **Text Box 1**.

Following from this, there is increasing evidence that the conformational dynamics of flexible loops [17, 60] and tunnels [61] can be exploited for protein design. For example, in 2019, Damborsky and collaborators published a study where ASR was used to revive a common ancestor of the *Renilla* luciferase and haloalkane dehalogenases [62]. The resurrected ancestor showed higher thermostability than both the extant enzymes (which is a common outcome of ASR, as discussed in the prior section), with the conformations visited during similar length MD simulations showing slower dynamics on the ancestor when compared to the modern enzymes. The activity for the monooxidase was only residual and the hydrolase activity was mostly lower

in the ancestor compared to their modern enzyme of choice. A recent continuation of this study [63] hypothesized that a helix at the tunnel mouth was controlling the rate of the monooxygenase activity. With an insertion variant of the ancestor and with a fragment grafted from the modern *Renilla* luciferase into the ancestor, it was possible to engineer the conformational dynamics of this luciferase to obtain both lower product inhibition, and highly stable bioluminescence [63], resulting in a more proficient reporter system for gene expression.

Enzyme Engineering from Protein Lego

While repurposing either extant or reconstructed ancestral enzymes for new catalytic functions has shown to be tremendously powerful as a starting point for protein design, repurposed enzymes could in principle also carry unnecessary (or even potentially undesirable) features for the desired function, which are just leftover traces of their evolutionary path. Therefore, substantial effort has also been invested into the design of new protein scaffolds, completely *de novo*, with a focus on obtaining tailored physico-chemical properties. The past decades witnessed tremendous progress in designing novel enzymes completely *de novo* by grafting minimal active sites onto pre-existing scaffolds [64]. However, the activities of the resulting constructs were typically low, with significant gains only obtained through subsequent directed evolution [6]. While it is unclear if *de novo* designer-scaffolds will necessarily provide more efficient enzymes, they have great potential to vastly expand the scope of new catalytic functionalities a scaffold can accommodate. This makes *de novo* protein design once again an exciting area, in particular as the field has matured significantly [65-67], with significant contributions also likely to be made from recent developments in protein structure prediction (such as Alpha Fold [68] and recent developments in protein structure prediction using a three-track neural network [69]).

Various approaches have been used to try to design new protein scaffolds [65-67], one of which is modular design in order to assemble new protein folds [70]. This approach is attractive because it effectively allows new proteins to be assembled as if they are made of molecular “LEGO ®” building blocks. Modular design is relevant from an evolutionary perspective, as there is increasing evidence that natural proteins evolve from fragments or motifs, such as short propellor-like motifs that have evolved into modern β -barrels [71], an omnipresent Rossmann ribose-binding motif that hints at common ancestry among Rossmann-fold enzymes that use ribose-based cofactors [72], and a β - α - β fragment that appears to be the minimal functional motif leading to modern P-loop NTPase and Rossmann enzymes [73], among other examples [74-76]. Therefore, modular design mimics the repeating themes that lead to the natural evolution of functional protein scaffolds.

Significant contributions to this area were made in early studies by Höcker, Sterner and colleagues [76-80], who helped elucidate the modular nature of protein evolution and develop the concept that even TIM-barrel folds could be amenable to structure-based recombination. As a more recent example, in 2016, Kuhlman and coworkers developed a design strategy they called SEWING [81], as this approach effectively “sews” together connected or disconnected pieces of existing proteins to create novel scaffolds. This allowed them to design highly stable α -helical proteins, showcasing the potential of the modular design approach. It was suggested that this approach can be used as a means with which to rapidly generate a wide variety of designable protein scaffolds. Related to this, Fleishman and coworkers have presented a novel approach, *AbDesign* [82], which assembles new backbone architectures by combining naturally occurring modular fragments, using the combinatorial backbone-conformational space of many protein families. This approach allows for the generation of a repertoire of scaffolds that exceeds the diversity of the entire Protein Data Bank

[83], for even a modestly sized family of homologs, giving the user significant control over the design process.

These provide just a few of many examples of the successful application of modular assembly to artificial protein design (for a summary of selected methods, see **Table 1**). However, natural evolution has also harnessed billions of years of evolution to generate a library of building blocks that can be identified recurrently across the protein universe. These are most commonly classified in terms of “domains”, typically comprising ~50-250 amino acids that represent an independent folding unit [84]. However, a number of studies have suggested that duplication and recombination of segments shorter than domains could have been the origin of the domains themselves, and are therefore the ultimate building blocks [71, 75, 81, 85, 86]. As has been argued for instance by Kolodny and coworkers [75], the proteins in the ancient universe were presumably shorter, but over extended periods of evolutionary time their sequences were afforded many “copy-paste” opportunities, leading to the scaffolds we observe today.

In parallel to these developments, there are now increasing efforts into constructing catalogues of locally similar segments across globally different domains (prior efforts, such as the Structural Classification of Protein Domains, SCOP [87], have focused on cataloguing full domains). As just some examples, Lupas and coworkers have constructed a vocabulary of ancient peptides that have led to modern folded proteins, borrowing from strategies to how linguists have compared modern languages to reconstruct ancient vocabularies [88]. Following from this, Kolodny and coworkers have presented a global view of the protein universe based on protein networks that connect domains that share fragments [89]. More recently, they have coined the concept of “themes”, as recurrent fragments of short protein segments of at least 35 amino acids that are unexpectedly

found in domains of independent evolutionary origin [75]. Along similar lines, Höcker and coworkers have developed the “Fuzzle” database [86], which was obtained by clustering the SCOPe95 database by sequence identity and performing a sequence- and structure-based comparison of all domains. This allowed the authors to identify 1337 fragments with lengths ranging from 11 to 229 amino acids, that populate a wide diversity of folds (519/1221 folds in the SCOP/Fuzzle database). A subsequent Python package, Protlego, uses the Fuzzle database to obtain evolutionarily conserved fragments for the automated and high-throughput *in silico* design of chimeric proteins [90]. Taken together, these approaches, some of which are summarized in **Figure 3**, pave the way for the construction of a catalogue of fragments that can be characterized by specific biophysical features, or even functional roles, such as metal-binding, nucleotide binding, or nucleic acid binding, on the basis of known structures [75, 88]. This, in turn, provides an extremely valuable resource for the facile design of custom-made proteins.

While modular design has frequently focused on generating novel stably folded proteins, there is also increasing interest in using this approach to generate functional enzymes. For example, in the case of *AbDesign* [82], Fleishman and coworkers were successfully able to use this approach for the development of stable and highly active new enzyme scaffolds. Specifically, they applied this approach to two TIM-barrel enzyme families with very different sequences, active-site structures and catalytic activities (GH10 and PLLs), and were able to obtain enzymes with similar catalytic and stability profiles as the natural enzymes for the GH10 designs, while for the PLLs some designs exhibited higher catalytic efficiencies than the natural enzymes, as well as broad substrate promiscuity. This was achieved by first segmenting all homologous structures within the protein family of interest (for example all GH10 xylanases) into modular parts, performing an “idealization” procedure which forces ideal bonds and relaxes the associated torsion angles,

computing backbone conformational databases based on this information as well as enforcing position-specific sequence constraints based on the results of multiple sequence alignment, performing a precomputation step involving the design and ranking of thousands of unique backbones, assembly of the resulting backbones, and, finally, performing stability optimization using PROSS [91] to generate a seamless structure. It is perhaps unsurprising that such a strategy would lead to highly efficient catalysts, as this appears to be the strategy also taken by nature itself in designing new proteins [74, 75, 89, 92]. However, it opens a new (and highly promising) door for evolutionary-based computational protein design.

Concluding Remarks

The past decade has witnessed an explosion of interest both in computational enzyme design, as well as, in parallel, in understanding the molecular evolution of enzyme function. These two developments are interlinked, as greater insight into how enzymes naturally emerge, evolve, and gain new functions, can be incorporated in turn to guide the design process: to borrow from Tawfik, “protein engineers turned evolutionists” [13]. While evolutionary insight is being used extensively to guide experimental protein design studies, it is only more recently also being incorporated into computational enzyme design, driven in part by increases in computational power that allow us to now model enzyme evolutionary trajectories in atomic detail, and pinpoint the physico-chemical parameters that shape the emergence of new functions.

This review has focused on three key directions being taken in the field: (1) the use of evolutionary information, gained through ancestral inference by bioinformatics analysis, to identify scaffolds that can be used as starting seeds for protein engineering, (2) increased appreciation of the role of

conformational dynamics and its importance in enzyme design and (3) renewed appreciation of and impetus towards modular design, following the modular nature of the natural emergence of new protein scaffolds. These three areas, in particular the first two, are both independently evolving sub-fields, but also highly interlinked. In addition, as these are all fast-growing areas, the list of studies presented here are by no means exhaustive, but rather are meant to showcase examples of success in the field. Finally, as a fast-growing field, there remain a number of outstanding questions that require addressing, some of which have been highlighted in the Outstanding Questions section.

The use of computational models to efficiently design new proteins has long been a major goal of computational biologists and chemists. Past decades have seen substantial progress in this area, both through the development of new methodologies and their successful application to protein design. We are at an exciting moment in the field as these investments are starting to bear fruit, and theory is becoming an indispensable component of the design process. As we demonstrate here, “turning evolutionist” is important also from a computational perspective, as learning from nature will allow us to circumvent significant remaining challenges in the field. Therefore, in time, there is likelihood that we will all become protein engineers turned evolutionists, exploiting evolutionary insight to guide the design process.

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References

1. Hellinga, H.W. and Richards, F.M. (1991) Construction of new ligand binding sites in proteins of known structure: I. Computer-aided modeling of sites with pre-defined geometry. *J. Mol. Biol.* 222, 763-785.
2. Dahiyat, B.I. and Mayo, S.L. (1996) Protein design automation. *Protein Sci.* 5, 895-903.
3. Voigt, C.A. et al. (2001) Computational method to reduce the search space for directed protein evolution. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA* 98, 3778-3783.
4. Looger, L.L. et al. (2003) Computational design of receptor and sensor proteins with novel functions. *Nature* 423, 185-190.
5. Currin, A. et al. (2015) Synthetic biology for the directed evolution of protein biocatalysts: navigating sequence space intelligently. *Chem. Soc. Rev.* 44, 1172-1239.
6. Kries, H. et al. (2013) *De novo* enzymes by computational design. *Curr. Opin. Chem. Biol.* 17, 221-228.
7. Lutz, S. and Iamurri, S.M. (2018) Protein engineering: Past, present and future. *Methods Mol. Biol.* 1685, 1-12.
8. Drienovská, I. and Roelfes, G. (2020) Expanding the enzyme universe with genetically encoded unnatural amino acids. *Nat. Catal.* 3, 193-202.
9. Marques, S.M. et al. (2021) Web-based tools for computational enzyme design. *Curr. Opin. Struct. Biol.* 69, 19-34.
10. Xu, Y. et al. (2020) Deep dive into machine learning models for protein engineering. *J. Chem. Inf. Mod.* 60, 2773-2790.
11. Chou, H.-H. et al. (2011) Diminishing returns epistasis among beneficial mutations decelerates adaptation. *Science* 332, 1190-1192.

12. Tokuriki, N. et al. (2012) Diminishing returns and tradeoffs constrain the laboratory optimization of an enzyme. *Nat. Commun.* 3, 1257.
13. Trudeau, D.L. and Tawfik, D.S. (2019) Protein engineers turned evolutionists - the quest for the optimal starting point. *Curr. Opin. Biotechnol.* 60, 46-52.
14. James, L.C. and Tawfik, D.S. (2003) Conformational diversity and protein evolution - a 60-year-old hypothesis revisited. *TRENDS Biochem. Sci.* 28, 361-368.
15. Maria-Solano, M.A. et al. (2018) Role of conformational dynamics in the evolution of novel enzyme function. *Chem. Commun.* 54, 6622-6634.
16. Campbell, E.C. et al. (2018) Laboratory evolution of protein conformational dynamics. *Curr. Opin. Struct. Biol.* 50, 49-57.
17. Crean, R.M. et al. (2020) Harnessing conformational plasticity to generate designer enzymes. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 142, 11324-11342.
18. Campitelli, P. et al. (2020) The role of conformational dynamics and allostery in modulating protein evolution. *Annu. Rev. Biophys.* 49, 267-288.
19. Romero-Romero, M.L. et al. (2016) Engineering ancestral protein hyperstability. *Biochem. J.* 473, 3611-3620.
20. Zou, T. et al. (2015) Evolution of conformational dynamics determines the conversion of a promiscuous generalist into a specialist enzyme. *Mol. Biol. Evol.* 32, 132-143.
21. Trudeau, D.L. et al. (2016) On the potential origins of the high stability of reconstructed ancestral proteins. *Mol. Biol. Evol.* 33, 2633-2641.
22. Spence, M.A. et al. (2021) Ancestral sequence reconstruction for protein engineers. *Curr. Opin. Struct. Biol.* 69, 131-141.

23. Selberg, A.G.A. et al. (2021) Ancestral sequence reconstruction: from chemical paleogenetics to maximum likelihood algorithms and beyond. *J. Mol. Evol.* 89, 157-164.
24. Randall, R.N. et al. (2016) An experimental phylogeny to benchmark ancestral sequence reconstruction. *Nat. Commun.* 7, 12847.
25. Bar-Rogovsky, H. et al. (2015) Assessing the prediction fidelity of ancestral reconstruction by a library approach. *Protein Eng. Des. Sel.* 28, 507-518.
26. Eick, G.N. et al. (2017) Robustness of reconstructed ancestral protein functions to statistical uncertainty. *Mol. Biol. Evol.* 34, 247-261.
27. Copley, S.D. (2021) Setting the stage for evolution of a new enzyme. *Curr. Opin. Struct. Biol.* 69, 41-49.
28. Thomas, A. et al. (2019) Highly thermostable carboxylic acid reductases generated by ancestral sequence reconstruction. *Commun. Biol.* 2, 429.
29. Wheeler, L.C. et al. (2016) The thermostability and specificity of ancient proteins. *Curr. Opin. Struct. Biol.* 38, 37-43.
30. Hillis, D.M. et al. (1992) Experimental phylogenetics: generation of a known phylogeny. *Science* 255, 589-592.
31. Gardner, J.M. et al. (2020) Manipulating conformational dynamics to repurpose ancient proteins for modern catalytic functions. *ACS Catal.* 10, 4863-4870.
32. Schupfner, M. et al. (2020) Analysis of allosteric communication in a multienzyme complex by ancestral sequence reconstruction. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA* 117, 346-354.
33. Maria-Solano, M.A. et al. (2021) Rational prediction of distal activity enhancing mutations in tryptophan synthase. *ChemRxiv*, DOI: 10.26434/chemrxiv.14151989.v1.

34. Gomez-Fernandez, B.J. et al. (2020) Consensus design of an evolved high-redox potential laccase. *Frontiers Bioeng. Biotechnol.* 8, 354.
35. Zamora, R.A. et al. (2020) Tuning of conformational dynamics through evolution-based design modulates the catalytic adaptability of an extremophile kinase. *ACS Catal.* 10, 10847-10857.
36. Gamiz-Arco, G. et al. (2021) Heme-binding enables allosteric modulation in an ancient TIM-barrel glycosidase. *Nat. Commun.* 12, 380.
37. Tokuriki, N. and Tawfik, D.S. (2009) Protein dynamism and evolvability. *Science* 324, 203-207.
38. Babbitt, A.C. et al. (2009) Efficient catalytic promiscuity for chemically distinct reactions. *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* 48, 3692-3694.
39. Bigley, A.N. and Rashel, M. (1834) Catalytic mechanisms for phosphotriesterases. *Biochim. Biophys. Acta* 1834, 443-453.
40. Osuna, S. (2020) The challenge of predicting distal active site mutations in computational enzyme design. *WIREs Comp. Mol. Sci.* 11, e1502.
41. Worthington, R.J. and Melander, C. (2013) Overcoming resistance to β -lactam antibiotics. *J. Org. Chem.* 78, 4207-4213.
42. Hall, B.G. and Barlow, M. (2003) Structure-based phylogenies of the serine beta-lactamases. *J. Mol. Evol.* 57, 255-260.
43. Risso, V.A. et al. (2013) Hyperstability and substrate promiscuity in laboratory resurrections of Precambrian β -lactamases. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 135, 2899-2902.
44. Modi, T. and Banu Ozkan, S. (2018) Mutations utilize dynamic allostery to confer resistance in TEM-1 β -lactamase. *Int. J. Mol. Sci.* 19, 3808.

45. Shah, A.A. et al. (2004) Characteristics, epidemiology and clinical importance of emerging strains of Gram-negative bacilli producing extended-spectrum beta-lactamases. *Res. Microbiol.* 155, 409-421.
46. Risso, V.A. et al. (2017) *De novo* active sites for resurrected Precambrian enzymes. *Nat. Commun.* 8, 16113.
47. Cortina, G.A. and Kasson, P.M. (2016) Excess positional mutual information predicts both local and allosteric mutations affecting beta lactamase drug resistance. *Bioinformatics* 32, 3420-3427.
48. Hart, K.M. et al. (2016) Modelling proteins' hidden conformations to predict antibiotic resistance. *Nat. Commun.* 7, 12965.
49. Risso, V.A. et al. (2020) Enhancing a *de novo* enzyme activity by computationally-focused ultra-low-throughput screening. *Chem. Sci.* 11, 6134-6148.
50. Khersonsky, O. et al. (2018) Automated design of efficient and functionally diverse enzyme repertoires. *Mol. Cell.* 72, 178-186.e5.
51. Bar-Even, A. et al. (2011) The moderately efficient enzyme: Evolutionary and physicochemical trends shaping enzyme parameters. *Biochemistry* 50, 4402-4410.
52. Korendovych, I.V. and DeGrado, W.F. (2014) Catalytic efficiency of designed catalytic proteins. *Curr. Opin. Struct. Biol.* 27, 113-121.
53. Broom, A. et al. (2020) Ensemble-based enzyme design can recapitulate the effects of laboratory directed evolution *in silico*. *Nat. Commun.* 11, 4808.
54. Blomberg, R. et al. (2013) Precision is essential for efficient catalysis in an evolved Kemp eliminase. *Nature* 503, 418-421.

55. Privett, H.K. et al. (2012) Iterative approach to computational enzyme design. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA* 109, 3790-3795.
56. Romero-Rivera, A. et al. (2017) Role of conformational dynamics in the evolution of retro-aldolase activity. *ACS Catal.* 7, 8524-8532.
57. Maria-Solano, M.A. et al. (2019) Deciphering the allosterically driven conformational ensemble in tryptophan synthase. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 141, 1409-13056.
58. Curado-Carballada, C. et al. (2019) Hidden conformations in *Aspergillus niger* monoamine oxidase are key for catalytic efficiency. *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* 2019, 3097-3101.
59. Acevedo-Rocha, C.G. et al. (2021) Pervasive cooperative mutational effects on multiple catalytic enzyme traits emerge via long-range conformational dynamics. *Nat. Commun.* 12, 1621.
60. Nestl, B.M. and Hauer, B. (2014) Engineering of flexible loops in enzymes. *ACS Catal.* 4, 3201-3211.
61. Kokkonen, P. et al. (2019) Engineering enzyme access tunnels. *Biotechnol. Adv.* 37, 107386.
62. Chaloupkova, R. et al. (2019) Light-emitting dehalogenases: reconstruction of multifunctional biocatalysts. *ACS Catal.* 9, 4810-4823.
63. Schenkmayerova, A. et al. (2021) Engineering the protein dynamics of an ancestral luciferase. *Nat. Commun.* 12, 3616.
64. Zanghellini, A. (2014) *De novo* computational enzyme design. *Curr. Opin. Biotechnol.* 29, 132-138.
65. Dawson, W.M. et al. (2019) Towards functional de novo designed proteins. *Curr. Opin. Chem. Biol.* 52, 102-111.
66. Korendovych, I.V. and DeGrado, W.F. (2020) De novo protein design, a retrospective. *Q. Rev. Biophys.* 53, e3.

67. Pan, X. and Kortemme, T. (2021) Recent advances in de novo protein design: Principles, methods, and applications J. Biol. Chem. 296, 100558.
68. Jumper, J. et al. (2021) Highly accurate protein structure prediction with AlphaFold. Nature Just Accepted, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-021-03819-2>.
69. Baek, M. et al. (2021) Accurate prediction of protein structures and interactions using a three-track neural network. Science Just Accepted, DOI: 10.1126/science.abj8754.
70. Lutz, S. and Benkovic, S.J. (2000) Homology-independent protein engineering. Curr. Opin. Biotechnol. 11, 319-324.
71. Smock, R.G. et al. (2016) *De novo* evolutionary emergence of a symmetrical protein is shaped by folding constraints. Cell 167, 476-486.
72. Laurino, P. et al. (2016) An ancient fingerprint indicates the common ancestry of Rossmann-fold enzymes utilizing different ribose-based cofactors. PLoS Biol. 14, e1002396.
73. Longo, L.M. et al. (2020) On the emergence of P-Loop NTPase and Rossmann enzymes from a Beta-Alpha-Beta ancestral fragment. eLife 9, e64415.
74. Kolodny, R. (2021) Searching protein space for ancient sub-domain segments. Curr. Opin. Struct. Biol. 68, 105-112.
75. Kolodny, R. et al. (2021) Briding themes: Short protein segments found in different architectures. Mol. Biol. Evol. 38, 2191-2208.
76. Höcker, B. et al. (2002) A common evolutionary origin of two elementary enzyme folds. FEBS Lett. 510, 133-135.
77. Höcker, B. et al. (2001) Dissection of a ($\beta\alpha$)₈-barrel enzyme into two folded halves. Nat. Struct. Biol. 8, 32-36.

78. Höcker, B. et al. (2004) Mimicking enzyme evolution by generating new (betaalpha)₈-barrels from (betaalpha)₄-half-barrels. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA* 101, 16448-16453.
79. Bharat, T.A.M. et al. (2008) A beta alpha-barrel built by the combination of fragments from different folds. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA* 105, 9942-9947.
80. Claren, J. et al. (2009) Establishing wild-type levels of catalytic activity on natural and artificial ($\beta\alpha$)₈-barrel protein scaffolds. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA* 106, 3704-3709.
81. Jacobs, T.M. et al. (2016) Design of structurally distinct proteins using strategies inspired by evolution. *Science* 352, 687-690.
82. Lipsh-Sokolik, R. et al. (2020) The AbDesign computational pipeline for modular backbone assembly and design of binders and enzymes. *Prot. Sci.* 30, 151-159.
83. Berman, H.M. et al. (2000) The Protein Data Bank. *Nucleic Acids Res.* 28, 235-242.
84. Wetlaufer, D.B. (1973) Nucleation, rapid folding, and globular intrachain regions in proteins. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA* 70, 697-701.
85. Lupas, A.N. et al. (2001) On the evolution of protein folds: are similar motifs in different protein folds the result of convergence, insertion, or relics of an ancient peptide world. *J. Struct. Biol.* 134, 191-203.
86. Ferruz, N. et al. (2020) Identification and analysis of natural building blocks for evolution-guided fragment-based protein design. *J. Mol. Biol.* 432, 3898-3914.
87. Murzin, A.G. et al. (1995) SCOP: a structural classification of proteins database for the investigation of sequences and structures. *J. Mol. Biol.* 247, 536-540.
88. Alva, V. et al. (2015) A vocabulary of ancient peptides at the origin of folded proteins. *eLife* 4, e09410.

89. Nepomnyachiy, S. et al. (2014) Global view of the protein universe. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA* 111, 11691-11696.
90. Ferruz, N. et al. (2021) Protlego: A Python package for the analysis and design of chimeric proteins . *Bioinformatics* In Press, DOI: 10.1093/bioinformatics/btab253.
91. Goldenzwig, A. et al. (2016) Automated structure- and sequence-based design of proteins for high bacterial expression and stability. *Mol. Cell* 63, 337-346.
92. Romero-Romero, S. et al. (2021) Evolution, folding, and design of TIM barrels and related proteins. *Curr. Opin. Struct. Biol.* 68, 94-104.
93. Hong, N.-S. et al. (2018) The evolution of multiple active site configurations in a designed enzyme. *Nat. Commun.* 9, 3900.
94. Nevin Gerek, Z. et al. (2013) Structural dynamics flexibility informs function and evolution at a proteome scale. *Evol. Appl.* 6, 423-433.
95. Wang, J. et al. (2020) Mapping allosteric communications within individual proteins. *Nat. Commun.* 11, 3862.
96. Schaeffer, R.D. et al. (2016) ECOD: New developments in the evolutionary classification of domains. *Nucleic Acids Res.* 45, D296-D230.

Glossary

Ancestral Sequence Reconstruction: statistical approach used in the study of protein evolution to predict the sequences of putative ancestors using the sequences of extant proteins.

Catalytic Promiscuity: ability of an enzyme to catalyze more than one, chemically distinct, reaction.

Conformational Ensemble: collection of structures that describe the conformational space a protein can sample.

Conformational Selection: functionally desirable shift in the conformational ensemble of a protein, triggered by ligand binding or amino acid substitutions/structural modifications to a protein.

Directed Evolution: protein engineering technique that iteratively introduces mutations into a protein, refining for a property of interest, thus mimicking the process of Darwinian evolution either *in vivo* or *in vitro*.

De Novo Design: in the context of enzyme design, designing a new scaffold with catalytic functionality, or a new active site in an existing scaffold, from first principles.

Distal Mutations: outer-sphere mutations of functional or catalytic importance.

Dynamic Allostery: regulation of the conformational properties of a protein.

Enzyme Evolvability: ability of an enzyme to adapt and acquire new functions upon mutation.

Evolutionary Trajectory: in the context of enzymes, the sequence of amino acid substitutions that take an enzyme from point A to B in sequence/function space.

Excess Positional Mutational Information Analysis: approach to obtain information about the inter-dependence of the positions of two variables in a system.

Machine Learning: branch of artificial intelligence in which an analytical model is designed to automatically self-improve upon the acquisition of new data.

Markov State Model: stochastic model used to describe the long-timescale dynamics of a molecular system.

Modular Design: in the context of protein design, this refers to design using protein fragments that are pieced together like molecular LEGO ® to (re)create a larger scaffold.

Optimization Plateau: in the context of directed evolution, a flat region of the search space where further improvements are challenging.

Population Shift: change in the conformational ensemble of a protein, usually triggered by either ligand binding or amino acid substitutions/structural modifications to a protein.

Productive and Non-Productive Conformations: conformations of a protein that are either beneficial or detrimental for a desired function (for the purposes of this review, catalytic function).

Structure vs. Sequence Based Design Approaches: for simplicity, we distinguish between approaches that primarily use structural information and those that primarily use sequence-information in the design process. Such a clean distinction is, however, not usually possible as there tends to be overlap between the two.

Text Box 1: Computational Tools to Predict Distal Mutations

Enzyme activity can be engineered through either substitutions made to active site residues, or to distal residues. In the first case, such substitutions typically change the shape of the binding pocket and/or modulate key interactions with the substrate, whereas in the latter case, distal mutations affect allosteric regulation of the enzyme and/or stabilize alternate active site configurations [16, 56, 93]. Although non-trivial, there is currently rapidly increasing interest in predicting distal mutations that can modulate enzyme activity [17, 40]. As such, there are a number of computational approaches that have shown promise as tools to reliably predict the allosteric effect of distal mutations. We will focus here on three of them: (1) the Dynamic Flexibility Index (DFI) [94], (2) the Shortest Path Map (SPM) approach [56] and (3) Ohm [95]. While all three approaches aim to predict long-range allosteric interaction networks, they use different sources of information to achieve this.

The DFI approach uses elastic network models to roughly sample different conformations of a protein [94]. Recently, this approach has been using not only structural information of one protein, but also proteins in the same phylogenetic branch to compare their dynamical properties, and assess which positions affect the function of the protein when substitutions occur [18]. The SPM approach [56] uses long timescale MD simulations to sample as much of the conformational ensemble as possible, and then uses that information to predict mutations that will have an allosteric effect on the protein's function. It was developed to study the role of dynamics in the evolution of enzymes. Finally, the Ohm web-tool is the most recent approach of the three, and requires less knowledge of the system and of computational tools for protein engineering [95]. This approach identifies allosterically important residues that are distal to the active site based on the position of the active site, the allosteric pathway connecting the position to the active site, and

the critical residues in between the active site and the allosteric site. Taken together, these examples showcase rapid progress in user-friendly computational tools that can be used to predict distal mutations that can alter the conformational landscape of an enzyme and thus regulate activity.

Figures

Figure 1. A comparison of representative structures extracted from 10 x 500 ns MD simulation of each of an ancestral glycosidase both (a) in the absence and (b) presence of heme, as well as (c) it's corresponding extant counterpart (in this case a glycosidase from *Halothermix orennii*). Shown here are also both the (d) absolute and (e) relative (heme-bound vs. non-heme bound ancestral glycosidase) root mean square fluctuations (RMSF, Å) of the backbone C_{α} -atoms of each relevant system. It can be seen from these simulations that there are clear differences in flexibility in the region spanning residues 227-334, both when comparing the ancestral and extant proteins, as well as the ancestral glycosidase with and without heme bound. This region corresponds to missing residues in the electron density of the ancestral protein, an effect which is particularly pronounced in the absence of heme. The corresponding rigidification of the ancestral protein by bound heme was shown, in turn, to lead to differences in catalytic activity. This figure was originally published in ref. [36]. Copyright 2018, Springer Nature. Published under a CC-BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>).

Figure 2. Enhancing the *de novo* Kemp eliminase activity of a Precambrian β -lactamase (GNCA4-WT) [46], using FuncLib [50]. (a) Biochemical characterization of the activity of the top 20 ranked variants obtained from FuncLib shows four variants with significant improvements in activity compared to the wild-type enzyme. The most efficient of these, GNCA4-12, of these has a turnover number (k_{cat}) of $\sim 10^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ and a catalytic efficiency (k_{cat}/K_M) of $\sim 2 \times 10^4 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ [49], which is comparable to the catalytic efficiency of the average modern enzyme towards its native substrate [51]. (b) An overlay of the crystal structures of the GNCA4-WT (tan) and GNCA-2 (light blue) β -lactamases, in complex with the transition state analog 6-nitrobenzotriazole, shows the overall scaffolds to be essentially superimposable, with only minor differences in side chain positioning at the *de novo* active site. Simulations of the reaction catalyzed by these enzymes indicate that enhancements in catalysis can be directly linked to improved positioning of the reacting fragments for optimal proton transfer at the Michaelis complex. As the catalytic D229 side chain is placed on a flexible loop, this positioning can likely be further improved by rigidifying the flexible loop. This figure was adapted from ref. [49]. Copyright 2020, Royal Society of Chemistry.

Figure 3. Schematic classification of current subdomain approaches. This figure shows the process of generation of different subdomain databases discussed in the main text. “Fragments” [88] used the SCOPe30 database as input and clusters by sequence similarity, yielding 40 clusters of fragments of about 35 amino acids in length. “Themes” [75] used ECOD (Evolutionary Classification of Protein Domains) [96] and the Protein Data Bank (PDB) [83] as input, clustered by sequence similarity, and performed C_{α} -RMSD calculations (3.5\AA threshold), obtaining 2195 curated hits of at least 35 amino acids. Finally, the “Fuzzle” [86] dataset is based on clustering of the SCOPe95 database by sequence identity combined with sequence and structure alignments, to yield 1337 fragments with lengths ranging from 11 to 229 amino acids. This figure was adapted from ref. [92], which was published under a CC-BY license. Copyright (2021), Elsevier.

Table 1. Overview of computational resources of relevance to enzyme design. Note that this list is based on a constantly expanding toolkit, and therefore it is impossible to be exhaustive.

Category	Name	Description	URL	Features and Limitations
ASR	Bali-phy	A standalone tool for the estimation of multiple sequence alignments and evolutionary trees.	http://www.bali-phy.org	<p>Features: Excellent performance on tested protein data sets.</p> <p>Limitations: Tends to systematically underalign on the biological sequence data.</p>
	IQ-TREE	Standalone software and web-tool for the inference of phylogenetic trees using the maximum likelihood approach.	http://www.iqtree.org	<p>Features: It is an integral component of many biomedical research open-source applications such as Galaxy, Nextstrain or QIIME 2.</p> <p>Limitations: Both IQ-Tree and RaxML-NG-inferred maximum likelihood gene trees have been suggested to have reproducibility issues.</p>

				y issues (DOI: 10.1038/s41467-020-20005-6).
	Molecular Evolutionary Genetics Analysis - MEGA X	User-friendly software for molecular evolution analysis and construction of phylogenetic trees.	https://www.megasoftware.net	Features: Easy to use GUI with good documentation available. Works across all platforms. Limitations: Works like a black box for some parameters, with no user control.
	MrBayes	A program for Bayesian inference and model choice across a wide range of phylogenetic and evolutionary models.	http://nbisweden.github.io/MrBayes	Features: GPU acceleration available. Limitations: Requires quite complex input data, which can hinder non-experts from performing ASR successfully.
	Phylogenetic Analysis by Maximum Likelihood - PAML	Standalone software and web-tool, to perform phylogenetic analysis using the maximum	http://abacus.gene.ucl.ac.uk/software/paml.html	Features: Has a GUI version, very customizable. Limitations: Steep learning curve for novice users.

		likelihood approach.		
	Randomized Axelerated Maximum Likelihood - RAxML	A standalone tool for ancestral sequence reconstruction using the maximum likelihood approach. A graphical user interface is being developed.	https://cme.hits.org/exelixis/web/software/raxml	<p>Features: Has a GUI interface (under development but already available for use).</p> <p>Limitations: Both IQ-Tree and RaxML-NG-inferred maximum likelihood gene trees have been suggested to have reproducibility issues (DOI: 10.1038/s41467-020-20005-6).</p>
	The FastML server - FastML	A web-tool for ancestral sequence reconstruction using the maximum likelihood approach.	http://fastml.tau.ac.il	<p>Features: Easy to use web-tool, can take unaligned sequences as input.</p> <p>Limitations: Accepts only the FASTA file format as input.</p>
Allostery	Dynamic Flexibility Index -	A protocol developed to identify	https://github.com/avishekrk/DFI	<p>Features: Code easily available and</p>

	DFI	per-residue contributions to a protein's overall dynamical profile.		ready to use. Limitations: Requires atomic coordinates.
	Ohm	Web-tool that predicts allosteric sites, inter-residue correlation, and identifies the allosteric pathways between them.	https://dokhlab.med.psu.edu/ohm/#	Features: Easy to use web-tool requiring only insertion of a 3D structure. Limitations: Structure-based predictions do not take dynamics into account.
	Shortest Path Map (SPM)	Tool developed for the identification of distal mutations affecting function, based on the shortest path map algorithm.	https://silviaosuna.wordpress.com/tools	Features: Uses long dynamic simulations to predict allosteric sites Limitations: Poor availability of the code
Databases (Assorted)	BRENDA	Electronic repository containing molecular and biochemical information on enzymes.	https://www.brenda-enzymes.org	Features: Several different queries are available as examples. Integrates CATH and SCOPe. Limitations:

				Requires login and there is a “professional” version.
	Protein Data Bank	A protein data bank containing more than 179 thousand macromolecular structures.	https://www.rcsb.org	Features: General database for protein structures obtained through NMR, X-ray crystallography and cryo-EM. Limitations: Contains redundant data and the search function could be better.
	UniProt	A central repository of protein data created by combining the Swiss-Prot, TrEMBL and PIR-PSD databases.	https://www.uniprot.org	Features: <i>De facto</i> go-to database for general protein information. Limitations: Overwhelming amount of data for newcomers.
Databases (Family Information)	CATH Protein Structure Classification database	A database containing information about the evolutionary relationships of protein	http://cathdb.info	Features: Huge open source database helps with automated implementati

		domains.		on in one's own workflows. Limitations: Drug compound information is still being developed.
	Fuzzle	A database containing evolutionary information about protein fragments.	https://fuzzle.uni-bayreuth.de	Features: Evolutionary information on fragments as opposed to full proteins only. Limitations: Hierarchical databases can lead to misclassification when slight differences are present in the sequences.
	Pfam	A database with information about protein families, represented by multiple sequence alignments generated using hidden Markov models.	http://pfam.xfam.org	Features: Constant development and integration with other EBI tools. Limitations: There is a high-quality database and a low-quality database that can lead to errors.
	Structural	A database	https://scop.mrc-lmb.cam.ac.uk	Features:

	Classification of Proteins - SCOP	of proteins classified based on structural relatednesses, such as superfamilies, families, and folds.		Uses data deposited in the PDB to group proteins. Curated to be non-redundant. Limitations: New version is not totally backwards compatible.
Modelling	AlphaFold	Protein prediction tool using neural networks. Achieved a score twice as good as the second-best protein predictor in CASP14 .	https://github.com/deepmind/alphafold	Features: New gold standard for protein structure prediction. Makes use of a newly developed neural network. Limitations: It is better where others were good, but still lacks good loop region predictions.
	iTasser	Both a web-tool and a standalone tool, it predicts protein structure using a hierarchical approach. It runs iteratively	https://zhanglab.dcmf.med.umich.edu/I-TASSER	Features: Good and easy to use webtool and a powerful standalone tool Limitations: Lacks accuracy when few templates are

		until the lowest energy structures are achieved and then uses publicly available function information to identify closely related templates with the same function.		available and is slower than similar options available.
	Modeller	Protein structure modelling tool that predicts structures by the satisfaction of spatial restraints obtained from a sequence alignment and shown as a probability density function.	https://salilab.org/modeller	Features: Can be installed on any platform and it is very fast in creating a new model. Limitations: Speed comes at the cost of accuracy for models where slower tools yield better results.
MSA	Clustal Omega	Multiple sequence alignment web-tool.	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/Tools/msa/clustalo	Features: Has been constantly developed since the 1980s for MSA.

				Limitations: Does not yield good results when a large amount of sequences is provided as input.
	Multiple Alignment Using Fast Fourier Transform - MAFFT	Multiple sequence alignment web-tool. Can also be used locally as a standalone tool.	https://mafft.cbrc.jp/alignment/software	Features: Users can choose between various multiple alignment methods. Limitations: It requires more memory to run.
	Multiple Sequence Comparison by Log-Expectation - MUSCLE	Multiple sequence alignment web-tool. As with Clustal Omega, it is integrated in the European Bioinformatics Institute (EBI) ecosystem.	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/Tools/msa/muscle	Features: Can achieve better average accuracy and speed than ClustalW2 or T-Coffee. Limitations: The Kimura distance used at the second stage, although fast, does not consider which changes of amino acids are occurring between sequences.
Protein Design	<i>AbDesign</i>	An algorithm	https://github.com/Fleishman-Lab/AbDesign_for_enzymes	Features: Stepwise

		for backbone design using structure- and sequence-based information.		workflow for the design of antibodies that focus on stability and binding affinity. Limitations: Requires sufficient sequence data on homologs as well as atomic coordinates.
	FuncLib	Web-tool to design and rank multiple point mutations based on evolutionary information and protein folding stability calculations.	https://funclib.weizmann.ac.il	Features: Multipoint variant design tool with an easy to use web server.. Limitations: Works better with a pre-stabilized protein scaffold. Poor knowledge of one's system may lead to poor results.
	Loop Grafter	A web-tool with a workflow to compare loop dynamics between proteins and transplant loops from one protein to another.	https://loschmidt.chemi.muni.cz/loop-grafter	Features: Automated way to transfer loops from one protein to the other. Limitations: Only works with the input of both the template and the scaffold

				proteins.
	PROSS - the Protein Repair One Stop Shop	A user-friendly web-tool to predict protein amino acid substitutions that yield higher stability variants.	https://pross.weizmann.ac.il/step/pross-terms	Features: Automated way to stabilize proteins by inserting mutations in the original protein. The method is reliable enough that only a more limited number of designs as output are sufficient. Limitations: Requires a structure (which may not always be available) for stability calculations.
	Protlego	A Python library for chimera design and analysis.	https://hoecker-lab.github.io/protlego	Features: Automatic construction and ranking of chimeras. Limitations: The correlation between structural features and experimental success is not yet clear.
	Rosetta	A comprehens	https://www.rosettacommons.org	Features: Encompasses

		ive software suite with several algorithms that can be used for the modelling and analysis of proteins.		many modules under the same umbrella name. Limitations: Not unified and developed by many people through the years, can be hard to implement and use different modules.
	SEWING	A protocol to design new tertiary protein structures by “sewing” together secondary structure building blocks.	https://klab.web.unc.edu/sewing-new-proteins	Features: Continuous and discontinuous SEWING can be merged to create additional diversity. Limitations: At present, it appears to have only been applied to the construction of all- α -helix chimeras.
Tunnels and Cavities	CAVER	Software tool for the analysis and visualization of tunnels and channels in protein	https://www.caver.cz	Features: Integration with other CaverSuite tools allows for deeper analysis Limitations:

		structure.		Still lacks the possibility to calculate pores.
	POVME	Standalone tool for ligand-binding pocket calculations	https://github.com/POVME/POVME	<p>Features: Calculates ligand-binding pockets using MD snapshots</p> <p>Limitations: The lack of a GUI makes it less accessible to non-bioinformaticians.</p>
Similarity Search	BLAST	A tool to calculate statistical significance between biological sequences.	https://blast.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/Blast.cgi	<p>Features: One of the most used tools for local alignment search. Fast and easy to use.</p> <p>Limitations: Developed in 1990, and has not changed substantially since then.</p>
	FASTA	A web-tool to provide a heuristic local search with a protein query.	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/Tools/sss/fastal/	<p>Features: First tool in the field. As with any other tool from EBI, it is integrated with many other tools and analyses.</p>

				<p>Newer tools exist that have evolved from this.</p> <p>Limitations: As opposed to BLAST, it does not remove low complexity regions.</p>
<p>Structure and Trajectory Data</p>	<p>Bio3D</p>	<p>R package for the analysis of protein structure and trajectory data. Provides a variety of approaches for conformational analysis of a protein.</p>	<p>http://thegrantlab.org/bio3d</p>	<p>Features: Comprehensive tool with many tutorials and easy installation.</p> <p>Limitations: Lack of GUI and a web-server makes for a steep learning curve for non-bioinformaticians.</p>